

TREATMENT OUTCOMES OF TUBERCULOSIS AND PATTERN OF DRUG RESISTANCE AMONG TYPE 2 DIABETES PATIENTS

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Abstract

The overall tuberculosis situation in the world remains a significant public health challenge due to its high prevalence, morbidity, and mortality rates. This study is focused on the association between tuberculosis and type II diabetes, which represents a complex interplay between two major global health threats. A total of 200 TB patients, with 100 in each group (diabetic and non-diabetic), were included in the final analysis. Diabetes was initially identified through random blood sample sugar testing using a glucometer and later confirmed with the HbA1c test. A fasting sputum sample was then obtained from each patient. The collected sample was used for smear microscopy of the TB, Culture, and GeneXpert® The MTB/RIF assay. At the four-month mark of anti-tuberculosis therapy, pharmacokinetic assessments were conducted to evaluate plasma drug concentrations. Overall, the mean age of the study participants has remained at 47.11±13.29 years. Baseline HbA1c showed that only 7% of patients had good glycemic control while the rest had poor glycemic control. A paired t-test was applied on the baseline and follow-up HbA1c findings and a significant difference (p -value <0.0001) was observed towards good glycemic control in follow-up. The treatment failure rate of diabetic patients is 13% much higher as compared to 6% in the non-diabetic group. Only five cases below the age of 40 years were categorized as treatment failure while 14/19 treatment failure cases were in the age group of ≥41 years. The findings of this current study indicate that Type II diabetes has a damaging effect on the outcomes of tuberculosis treatment. Diabetic patients have an increased rate of treatment failure compared to non-diabetic individuals (13% vs. 6%). Tuberculosis therapy was further complicated by the widespread presence of inadequate glycemic control among diabetes

patients. These findings emphasize the significance of providing comprehensive care that addresses both tuberculosis and diabetes to enhance treatment results, especially in areas with a significant prevalence of both conditions. Thus, further analysis and research on this topic are required to understand the mechanisms affecting the metabolism of anti-TB drugs in diabetic patients.

INTRODUCTION

Tuberculosis (TB), caused by *Mycobacterium tuberculosis*, remains one of the leading causes of morbidity and mortality worldwide [1,2]. In 2019, nearly 10 million new cases and 1.4 million deaths were reported globally [3]. TB primarily affects the lungs but can also involve extra-pulmonary sites. Transmission occurs through airborne droplets, making overcrowded and resource-limited settings especially vulnerable [4].

The disease burden is disproportionately higher in low- and middle-income countries, where poverty, malnutrition, and inadequate healthcare access fuel transmission [5]. The emergence of multidrug-resistant (MDR-TB) and extensively drug-resistant TB (XDR-TB) further complicates management and increases healthcare costs [6]. Sub-Saharan Africa, Southeast Asia, and the Western Pacific remain high-burden regions, where TB is often compounded by comorbidities such as HIV and diabetes mellitus [7-9]. Diabetes mellitus (DM) has emerged as a major risk factor for TB. It impairs host immunity, increases the risk of latent TB infection progressing to active disease, and worsens treatment outcomes [10,11]. Evidence shows that individuals with diabetes are nearly three times more likely to develop TB and face higher risks of relapse, delayed sputum conversion, and mortality [12,13].

The biological interaction between TB and DM is multifactorial. Chronic hyperglycemia weakens macrophage and T-cell responses, while inflammatory and metabolic changes further compromise host defense [14,15]. Mycobacterial proteins may also promote insulin resistance and alter immune regulation, complicating disease control [16]. This dual burden contributes to poor treatment response and a higher risk of drug resistance [17].

The coexistence of TB and diabetes therefore represents a growing public health challenge, particularly in regions with limited resources.

Integrated approaches that combine TB control with diabetes care are urgently needed [18,19]. This study aims to evaluate the clinical and pharmacological implications of TB in diabetic patients, with particular emphasis on treatment outcomes and drug interactions, to inform better management strategies.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

This prospective cohort study was carried out over six months at the University of Haripur in collaboration with the NIH-Health Research Institute (HRI) TB Research Centre, King Edward Medical University/Mayo Hospital, Lahore. Ethical approval was obtained from the institutional review board, and written informed consent was secured from all participants. Clinically diagnosed and microbiologically confirmed TB patients, newly initiated on anti-tuberculosis therapy (ATT), were enrolled and stratified into diabetic and non-diabetic groups. Diabetes status was assessed using a glucometer (cut-off >140 mg/dL) and confirmed by HbA1c testing, for which 3 mL of venous blood was collected in EDTA tubes. HbA1c levels were measured at baseline and repeated after four months of ATT to monitor glycemic changes.

Baseline sputum specimens were collected in sterile containers and processed for smear microscopy, culture, and molecular diagnosis. Smears were prepared, stained with Auramine-Rhodamine, and examined by fluorescence microscopy for acid-fast bacilli. Decontaminated samples using the NALC-NaOH method were inoculated onto Löwenstein-Jensen (LJ) medium and incubated at 37 °C for up to eight weeks. GeneXpert MTB/RIF assay was performed for rapid detection of *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* and rifampicin resistance, and drug susceptibility testing was conducted on LJ medium using the proportion method against isoniazid, rifampicin, streptomycin, and ethambutol. The

H37Rv strain served as a control for quality assurance.

At the fourth month of ATT, pharmacokinetic assessments were conducted to evaluate plasma drug concentrations. Venous blood samples were obtained 2–8 hours after drug administration, centrifuged, and stored at –20 °C until analysis. Plasma concentrations of isoniazid and rifampicin were quantified using high-performance liquid chromatography (HPLC). The primary treatment outcome was sputum smear conversion at two months, while secondary outcomes included pharmacokinetic parameters and their association with glycemic status.

Data were entered in Microsoft Excel and analyzed using SPSS (latest version, IBM Corp., Armonk, NY, USA). Continuous variables were expressed as mean ± standard deviation, and categorical variables as frequencies and percentages. Statistical significance was assessed using chi-square or Fisher’s exact test for categorical variables and Student’s t-test for continuous variables, with a p-value of <0.05 considered significant.

RESULTS

This chapter contains the result of the topic treatment outcomes of tuberculosis and pattern of drug resistance among type 2 diabetes patients.

The analysis of data shows that a total of 200 confirmed TB patients comprising 100 each in diabetic and non-diabetic groups were considered for final analysis. Of these 91 were females and 109 were males making a female-to-male ratio of 1:1.2 in this study.

Table 4.1 compares non-diabetic and diabetic participants based on HbA1c levels, smear grading, culture findings, and Gene-Xpert results. Among the participants, all non-diabetics fell into the non-diabetic HbA1c category, while the majority of diabetics (93%) had poor glycemic control. Smear positivity was predominantly at the 1+ grade in both groups (69%). Culture results showed the majority with 1+ growth (82.5%), while Gene-Xpert revealed most cases as medium detection (79%), with fewer in low or high detection categories.

Table 4.1: This table compares non-diabetic and diabetic participants based on HbA1c categories, smear results, culture results, and Gene-Xpert outcomes.

Characteristics		Group				Total	
		Non-Diabetic		Diabetic			
		N	%	N	%	n	%
HbA1c category	Non-Diabetic	100	100.0	0	0.0	100	50.0
	Good Control	0	0.0	7	7.0	7	3.5
	Poor Control	0	0.0	93	93.0	93	46.5
Smear Result	Scanty (1-10 AFB)	8	8.0	8	8.0	16	8.0
	1+	69	69.0	69	69.0	138	69.0
	2+	22	22.0	19	19.0	41	20.5
	3+	1	1.0	4	4.0	5	2.5
Culture Result	1-10 CFU	2	2.0	0	0.0	2	1.0
	1+ (10-100 CFU)	76	76.0	89	89.0	165	82.5
	2+ (100-200 CFU)	22	22.0	11	11.0	33	16.5
Gene-Xpert Result	Detected Low	11	11.0	7	7.0	18	9.0
	Detected Medium	75	75.0	83	83.0	158	79.0
	Detected High	14	14.0	10	10.0	24	12.0

Table 4.2 presents the mean baseline and follow-up HbA1c levels, along with the maximum plasma concentrations (C_{max}) of isoniazid and rifampicin in non-diabetic and diabetic participants. Diabetics showed higher HbA1c at both baseline (7.22 vs.

4.65) and follow-up (6.69 vs. 4.46) compared to non-diabetics. The C_{max} of isoniazid was comparable between the two groups (7.55 vs. 7.37 µg/ml), whereas rifampicin levels were higher among diabetics (3.72 vs. 2.89 µg/ml).

Table 4.2: Mean baseline and follow-up HbA1c levels, along with the maximum concentration (C_{max}) of isoniazid and rifampicin in non-diabetic and diabetic participants.

Variables	Group				Overall	
	Non-Diabetic		Diabetic			
	Mean	Stand. Dev.	Mean	Stand. Dev	Mean	Stand. Dev
Baseline HbA1C	4.65	0.51	7.22	0.47	5.94	1.38
Follow-up HbA1c	4.46	0.37	6.69	0.73	5.58	1.26
C _{max} Isoniazid (µg/ml)	7.55	0.22	7.37	0.26	7.46	0.26
C _{max} Rifampicin (µg/ml)	2.89	0.26	3.72	0.18	3.30	0.47

Table 4.3 presents the results of a paired t-test comparing baseline and follow-up HbA1c levels among participants. The analysis showed a mean reduction of 0.36 units with a standard deviation of 0.55. The 95% confidence interval (0.28-0.44) confirmed that this reduction was consistent across

the sample. The test statistic (t = 9.228, df = 199, p < 0.001) indicates that the decrease in HbA1c from baseline to follow-up was highly significant, suggesting that treatment or follow-up measures effectively improved glycemic control over time.

Table 4.3: Paired t-test results comparing baseline and follow-up HbA1c levels. The 95% confidence interval and t-value further support the result.

Paired Sample t-test	Paired Differences				T	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	
	Mean	Std. Dev.	Std. Error of the Mean	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference				
				Lower	Upper			
Baseline HbA1C - Follow-up HbA1c	.36200	.55479	.03923	.28464	.43936	9.228	199	.000

Table 4.4 illustrates the distribution of follow-up HbA1c categories among non-diabetic and diabetic participants. All non-diabetic individuals (100%) remained in the non-diabetic range. Among

diabetics, more than half (54%) achieved good glycemic control, while 46% continued to show poor control. Overall, half of the participants fell in the

non-diabetic category, 27% in good control, and 23% in poor control at follow-up.

Table 4.4: Distribution of follow-up HbA1c categories among non-diabetic and diabetic participants.

HbA1c category	Group				Total	
	Non-Diabetic		Diabetic			
	N	%	N	%	N	%
Non-Diabetic	100	100.0	0	0.0	100	50.0
Good Control	0	0.0	54	54.0	54	27.0
Poor Control	0	0.0	46	46.0	46	23.0

Table 4.5 presents the independent sample t-test results comparing the maximum plasma concentrations (Cmax) of isoniazid and rifampicin between non-diabetic and diabetic participants. For isoniazid, the mean difference was 0.18 µg/ml (95% CI: 0.12–0.25), which was statistically significant (t = 5.31, p < 0.001), indicating that non-diabetic participants had slightly higher drug levels compared

to diabetics. In contrast, rifampicin showed a significant negative mean difference of -0.83 µg/ml (95% CI: -0.90 to -0.77), with diabetics exhibiting higher concentrations than non-diabetics (t = -26.48, p < 0.001). These findings suggest that diabetes status affects the pharmacokinetics of these drugs differently, with non-diabetics achieving higher levels of isoniazid, while diabetics attain higher levels of rifampicin.

Table 4.5: Results of independent sample t-test assessing the maximum concentrations (Cmax) of Isoniazid and Rifampicin.

		Levene's Test for Equality of Variances		t-test for Equality of Means						
		F	Sig.	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	SE Dif	95% CI of the Difference	
									Lower	Upper
Cmax Isoniazid	Equal variances assumed	1.702	0.194	5.306	198	.000	.18340	.03456	.11524	.25156
	Equal variances not assumed			5.306	8	.000	.18340	.03456	.11523	.25157
Cmax Rifampicin	Equal variances assumed	15.72		-26.482	198	.000	-.83300	.03145	-.89503	-.77097

	Equal variances not assumed	3	0.000	26.482	176.933	0.000	.83300	.03145	.89507	.77093
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Table 4.6 summarizes the treatment outcomes of tuberculosis patients in relation to their diabetic status. Among non-diabetic participants, the majority (71%) successfully completed treatment, 23% were cured, and 6% experienced treatment failure. In comparison, diabetic patients showed slightly lower success rates, with 60% completing treatment and

27% being cured, while treatment failure was more than double that of non-diabetics (13% vs. 6%). Overall, across both groups, 65.5% completed treatment, 25% were cured, and 9.5% experienced failure. These results suggest that diabetes may negatively influence TB treatment success, with higher rates of failure observed in diabetic patients.

Table 4.6: Treatment Outcomes for two groups of tuberculosis patients: non-diabetic and diabetic.

Outcome Parameters	Group				Total	
	Non-Diabetic		Diabetic		n	%
	N	%	N	%		
Cured	23	23.0	27	27.0	50	25.0
Treatment Completed	71	71.0	60	60.0	131	65.5
Failure	6	6.0	13	13.0	19	9.5

Table 4.7 compares glycemic control, categorized by HbA1c levels, with treatment outcomes among tuberculosis patients. Among non-diabetic participants, 46% were cured, 54.2% completed treatment, and 31.6% experienced failure. In the good glycemic control group, half of the patients (50%) were cured, 22.1% completed treatment, and 15.8% failed therapy. In contrast, poor glycemic

control was strongly associated with adverse outcomes, as only 4% achieved cure, 23.7% completed treatment, while more than half (52.6%) experienced treatment failure. These findings highlight that poor glycemic control is a major risk factor for unsuccessful TB treatment outcomes compared to good control or non-diabetic status.

Table 4. 7: Comparison of Glycemic Control, categorized by HbA1c levels, with treatment outcomes among tuberculosis patients.

HbA1c category	Treatment Outcomes							
	Cured		Treatment Completed		Failure		Total	
	N	%	n	%	n	%	n	%
Non-Diabetic	23	46.0	71	54.2	6	31.6	100	50.0
Good Control	25	50.0	29	22.1	3	15.8	54	27.0
Poor Control	2	4.0	31	23.7	10	52.6	46	23.0

Table 4.8 presents treatment outcomes for tuberculosis patients categorized by age groups. Among participants aged ≤ 40 years, 22.4% were cured, 69% completed treatment, and 8.6% experienced failure. In contrast, patients aged ≥ 41 years showed slightly better cure and completion rates, with 26.1% cured, 64.1% completing

treatment, and 9.8% failing treatment. Overall, out of 200 patients, 25% were cured, 65.5% completed treatment, and 9.5% experienced treatment failure. These findings indicate that treatment outcomes were broadly similar across age groups, though younger patients had a slightly higher treatment completion rate, while older patients demonstrated marginally higher cure and failure rates.

Table 4.8: Treatment outcomes for tuberculosis patients categorized by age groups: ≤ 40 Years and ≥ 41 Years.

Age Group	Treatment Outcomes			Total
	Cured	Treatment Completed	Failure	
≤ 40 Years	13	40	5	58
≥ 41 Years	37	91	14	142
Total	50	131	19	200

Table 4.9 categorizes treatment outcomes based on the duration of diabetes among tuberculosis patients. For those with a diabetes duration of ≤ 5 years, 38.1% were cured, 57.1% completed treatment, and

only 4.8% experienced failure. In contrast, patients with a diabetes duration of ≥ 6 years had markedly poorer outcomes: just 8.1% were cured, 64.9% completed treatment, and a high proportion (27%) experienced treatment failure. Overall, among 100 diabetic patients, 27% were cured, 60% completed treatment, and 13% failed therapy. These findings indicate that a longer duration of diabetes is strongly associated with unfavorable TB treatment outcomes, particularly higher failure rates.

Table 4.9: Categorization of treatment outcomes based on the duration of diabetes among patients.

Duration of Diabetes	Treatment Outcomes			Total
	Cured	Treatment Completed	Failure	
≤ 5 Years	24	36	3	63
≥ 6 Years	3	24	10	37
Total	27	60	13	100

Table 4.10 presents the follow-up culture results of tuberculosis patients categorized by diabetes status. Among non-diabetic patients, the vast majority (94%) had negative cultures, with only a few showing residual bacterial growth: 4% with 1-10 CFU, 1%

with 1+ (10-100 CFU), and 1% with 2+ (100-200 CFU). In diabetic patients, 87% achieved negative cultures, while 1% had 1-10 CFU, 8% showed 1+, and 4% demonstrated 2+ growth. Overall, across both groups, 90.5% of patients had negative

cultures, whereas 9.5% remained culture positive, with diabetics more likely to show residual bacterial

growth compared to non-diabetics.

Table 4.10: Follow-up Culture Results for tuberculosis patients, categorized by diabetes status: Non-Diabetic and Diabetic.

Follow up Culture	Group				Total	
	Non-Diabetic		Diabetic			
	N	%	N	%	n	%
Negative	94	94.0	87	87.0	181	90.5
1-10 CFU	4	4.0	1	1.0	5	2.5
1+ (10-100 CFU)	1	1.0	8	8.0	9	4.5
2+ (100-200 CFU)	1	1.0	4	4.0	5	2.5
3+ (>200 CFU)	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0

Table 4.11 shows the drug susceptibility profiles of culture-positive tuberculosis cases by diabetes status. Resistance to rifampicin was universal, with 100% of both non-diabetic and diabetic patients showing resistance. For isoniazid, resistance was also high, observed in 83.3% of non-diabetics and 84.6% of diabetics, while only a small fraction remained sensitive (16.7% and 15.4%, respectively). In contrast, ethambutol retained good sensitivity, with all non-diabetics (100%) and most diabetics (92.3%) responding, though resistance appeared in a small

proportion of diabetics (7.7%). Similarly, for streptomycin, sensitivity was seen in 83.3% of non-diabetics and 76.9% of diabetics, with resistance in 16.7% and 23.1%, respectively. Overall, the findings highlight a high burden of multi-drug resistance (MDR-TB), particularly against rifampicin and isoniazid, with slightly greater resistance patterns observed among diabetics.

Table 4.11: Drug Susceptibility drug susceptibility profiles of culture-positive tuberculosis cases categorized by diabetes status: Non-Diabetic and Diabetic.

Drugs		Group				Total	
		Non-Diabetic		Diabetic			
		n	%	N	%	n	%
Isoniazid	Sensitive	1	16.7	2	15.4	3	15.8
	Resistant	5	83.3	11	84.6	16	84.2
Rifampicin	Sensitive	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0
	Resistant	6	100.0	13	100.0	19	100.0
Ethambutol	Sensitive	6	100.0	12	92.3	18	94.7
	Resistant	0	0.0	1	7.7	1	5.3
Streptomycin	Sensitive	5	83.3	10	76.9	15	78.9
	Resistant	1	16.7	3	23.1	4	21.1

Figure 4.1: The data highlight the proportion of male and female participants, providing a comparative overview of gender representation.

Figure 4.2: Comparative analysis of the average age of male and female participants within each group (Diabetic and Non-Diabetic), allowing for a clear visualization of age-related differences between genders.

DISCUSSION

Our research objectives and main findings underscore the importance of glycemic control in the effective treatment of TB in diabetic patients. Glucose and its related parameters are critical

forecasters for clinical outcomes following complications with other diseases. This study supports the findings of Ching-Hui Sia et al. on the Asian population, which shows that 5.6% of the

population demonstrates good glycemic control while the rest have poor control monitored by HbA1C testing [20]. A study conducted by Urina-Jassir in 2021 shows that 85% of TB-positive patients have co-morbidity with diabetes mellitus. This specifies that there is a significant association between diabetes mellitus and tuberculosis, suggesting that a considerable portion of TB patients are also managing diabetes as an underlying health condition [21].

Our findings regarding plasma concentrations of rifampicin and isoniazid align with earlier studies. Diabetes mellitus contributes to variation in rifampicin concentration, although no significant difference was found in maximum plasma concentration between diabetic and non-diabetic patients. Similar to previous research, our study found that diabetic TB patients had a higher risk of low rifampicin plasma concentrations compared to non-diabetics [22,23].

Treatment failure rates were observed to be higher among diabetics (13%) compared to non-diabetics (6%). Although statistically insignificant, the more than two-fold difference is clinically important. These results are consistent with previous studies such as Wang et al., which reported that type 2 diabetes negatively impacts TB treatment outcomes [24]. Diabetes has been linked to increased risks of treatment failure, death, and relapse, as well as delayed sputum culture conversion [25]. Comparable findings were also reported by studies from Malaysia [26], Ethiopia [27], and India [28], all of which highlighted poorer TB outcomes in patients with diabetes mellitus.

In our study, poor glycemic control was strongly associated with treatment failure, where 52.6% of failure cases occurred in poorly controlled diabetic patients. This supports the findings of M.J. Magee et al., who reported that poor glycemic control significantly impacts TB treatment outcomes [29]. Hyperglycemia impairs immune response, delays recovery, increases complications, and can contribute to treatment failure. Other research also confirms that high blood sugar levels can delay recovery, increase complications, and sometimes lead to treatment failure [30,31].

Age also appeared to influence TB outcomes, with older patients more likely to experience treatment

failure due to comorbidities and reduced immunity. This is in line with previous literature, which confirms that type 2 diabetes and TB co-infection is more common in older adults [32,33]. Similarly, the duration of diabetes was a critical factor, as patients with a longer history of diabetes (≥ 6 years) had significantly worse outcomes compared to those with a shorter duration (≤ 5 years).

Drug resistance patterns in this study highlight the clinical challenge of managing TB in diabetic patients. Resistance to rifampicin was universal among failure cases, and most were also resistant to isoniazid. These findings are consistent with WHO reports, which emphasize Pakistan's high TB burden and rising multidrug-resistant TB cases [34]. Factors such as delayed diagnosis, inappropriate regimens, and inadequate follow-up contribute to the emergence of resistance.

Overall, our findings stress the importance of routine screening and integrated management of diabetes in TB patients. Addressing both diseases concurrently could improve treatment outcomes, reduce drug resistance, and ultimately enhance patient survival.

Conclusion

Diabetic TB patients have over twice the treatment failure rate compared to non-diabetic TB patients, especially with poor glycemic control and longer diabetes duration (≥ 6 years). Age showed no significant effect, and plasma drug levels of isoniazid and rifampicin were similar in both groups. The findings stress the need for integrated diabetes and TB management, routine screening, and strict glycemic monitoring to improve outcomes.

Recommendations

Monitor and control blood glucose in diabetic TB patients throughout treatment.

Screen all TB patients for diabetes at diagnosis.

Tailor TB regimens for diabetic patients considering altered drug response.

Update TB guidelines to integrate diabetes management.

Prioritize early intervention for patients with long-standing diabetes (≥ 6 years).

Train healthcare workers on TB-diabetes management complexities.

Support further research on drug metabolism and

glycemic control strategies.

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